

Proximate and phytochemical analyses of raw and differently processed pigeon pea seeds as potential animal feed

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Abstract

Proximate and Phytochemical analyses of Raw and differently processed Pigeon pea seeds as potential Animal feed was conducted at the Nutritional Laboratory of Food Science and Technology, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*) as the test ingredient was obtained from local markets in Owo. The seeds were handpicked and winnowed to remove all the foreign materials, after which the seeds were processed using the following methods; soaking, boiling, and toasting at different times (24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours soaked; 15 minutes, 30 minutes, and 45 minutes boiled; 5 minutes, 10 minutes, and 45 minutes toasted). Proximate and phytochemical analyses were carried out using standard methods of analysis. The results revealed that the anti-nutritional factors in the processed pigeon pea seed meal (PPSM) had a lower range for oxalate (0.81-2.07mg/g), phytic acid (0.46-9.02mg/g), saponin (0.85-2.97mg/g), tannin (0.21-1.35%), and trypsin inhibitor (1.01-13.11%) as against 2.43mg/g, 10.71mg/g, 24.72mg/g, 4.17%, and 29.40% obtained for raw pigeon pea seed meal, respectively. It was concluded that processing (soaking, boiling, and toasting) of PPSM reduced the level of anti-nutritional factors (oxalate, phytate, saponin, tannin, and trypsin inhibitor), and thus the inclusion of processed pigeon pea seed meal is recommended as an ingredient in animal feed as it offers high nutritive value due to its high crude protein content. Also, processing by soaking, boiling, or toasting as analyzed in this study is recommended to reduce the content of its anti-nutritional factors.

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Introduction

The pigeon pea is a leguminous plant from the Fabaceae family that was introduced to America and East Africa about 3000 years ago from Asia. It is referred to as "Wake masa" by the Hausa, "Fiofio" by the Igbo, "Otili" by the Yoruba, and "Agwugwu" by the Igalas in Nigeria, where it is produced on a yearly basis in quantities of about 147 tonnes (Oke, 2014).

Pigeon pea seeds include various dietary components and comprise 85% cotyledons, 14% seed coat, and roughly 1% embryo (Singh *et al.*, 2020). In most markets throughout Nigeria, pigeon pea is readily available. Still, due to geographic location, cultivar, growth conditions, and storage conditions, there is a significant variation in the chemical makeup of the crop (Fatokimi and Tanimonure 2021).

One of the most popular legumes grown for its palatable seeds in tropical and subtropical regions is the pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Mill.). the pigeon pea is drought resistant, tough, and quick to adapt (Saxena *et al.*, 2020). In areas where rain failures are common, drought resistance might be thought of as being of the utmost importance for food security (Semba *et al.*, 2021).

Despite being a significant legume, the pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*) has very little appeal to humans as a food source due to the availability and more palatable flavour of other, simpler-to-cook beans like cowpea. Right now in Nigeria, it serves no industrial purpose. Up to 30% of livestock have found it to be a suitable source of protein (Amaefule *et al.*, 2011). However, the presence of anti-nutritional elements such as trypsin inhibitors, chymotrypsin inhibitors, amylase inhibitors, haemagglutinins, tannins (polyphenols), saponins, cyanide, phytic acid, oxalate, etc. may make the use of pigeon pea seed in monogastric feeding problematic. (Duhan and others, 2001; Igene *et al.*, 2012), which affects the legume's bitter or unpleasant taste and reduces its ability to digest proteins and absorb divalent metal ions like Fe²⁺ and Zn²⁺ in the colon (Abdu *et al.*, 2008). In order to fully utilize pigeon pea seeds as a feed ingredient, it is crucial to remove these unwanted components. At this time,

boiling, boiling and de-hulling, toasting, and roasting are the main procedures used to process raw pigeon pea seeds (Akintunde *et al.*, 2010; Yisa *et al.*, 2010).

Objective of the Research

The objective of this research is to determine the proximate and some phytochemical compositions of raw and processed pigeon pea seeds.

Materials and methods

Experimental site

The study was carried out at the Nutritional Laboratory of Food Science and Technology, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Source and preparation of test ingredients

The test component, pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*), was purchased at neighbourhood markets in Owo, Ondo State, Nigeria. The seeds were hand-selected, winnowed to remove any foreign materials, and then processed by soaking, boiling, and toasting them at various times (for example, for 24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours; for 15 minutes, 30 minutes, and 45 minutes; and for 5 minutes, 10 minutes, and 45 minutes, respectively).

Raw pigeon pea seed meal

After being cleaned, the raw pigeon pea seeds were ground into a meal known as raw pigeon pea seed meal (RPPM) using a hammer mill equipped with a 0.2mm sieve. RPPM was kept in an airtight container and then its proximate and phytochemical composition was determined.

Soaking of pigeon pea seeds

In order to create three different types of soaked pigeon pea seed meal (SPPM), 15kg of pigeon pea seeds were soaked in 75 litres of clean water for 24 hours, 48 hours, and 72 hours, respectively, in three different drums. After the water was drained off, the soaked seeds were sun-dried for 4 days during the dry season.

Boiling of pigeon pea seeds

On a gas cooker, 25 litres of cold, clean water were heated to boiling, and 15 kg of raw pigeon pea seeds were added. The water was then covered and allowed

to boil for 15, 30, and 45 minutes, respectively. The instant the pigeon pea seed was added to the boiling water, the process of boiling began (Audu and Aremu, 2011). After the seeds had boiled for the specified amount of time, the water was drained out, and they were left to dry in the sun for 4 days. During the dry season, the sun-dried seeds were ground into 3 different kinds of boiled pigeon pea seed meal (BPPM).

Toasting of pigeon pea seed

The eroded fine sand was placed in a sizable frying pan over a fire, and pigeon pea seeds were added. The seeds were stirred continuously for 5 minutes, 10 minutes, and 15 minutes, respectively, to toast them until they were a golden brownish colour. To obtain three different varieties of toasted pigeon pea seed (TPPM), the toasted seeds were separated from the sand and allowed to cool for an additional 30 minutes.

Proximate analysis

Proximate analyses of the experimental samples were carried out according to AOAC (2012).

Phytochemical analyses

Standard analytical techniques were used for the phytochemical analyses; phytate was determined in accordance with Maga (1983), oxalates in accordance with Soetan *et al.*, trypsin inhibitor in accordance

with Liener (1980), tannin in accordance with Makkar and Goodchild (1996), and saponin in accordance with Brunner (1984).

Statistical analysis

Using a completely randomized design and analysis of variance (ANOVA), the data were acquired (S.A.S., 2012). Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) distinguished between significant means. The overall confidence threshold for testing statistical significance was set at 5%.

Result

Table (I) lists the chemical make-up of the test components (raw and processed pigeon pea seed meal). Crude protein (28.10 to 30.51%), ether extract (2.10 to 2.21%), crude fiber (7.49 to 10.11%), ash (4.81-5.61%), nitrogen-free extract (44.42 to 50.11%), and dry matter (86.61 to 91.96%) are the ranges of proximate composition. All the parameters evaluated revealed that there were significant ($p < 0.05$) differences. Oxalate, phytic acid, saponin, tannin, and trypsin inhibitor levels were each reduced by roughly 95.32% as a result of processing pigeon pea seed meal (PPSM), which also decreased the other anti-nutritional elements evaluated.

Table I. Chemical and Phytochemical compositions of the raw and differently processed pigeon pea seed meal.

Parameters	Soaking time					Boiling time					Toasting time				
	Raw	24hrs	48hrs	72hrs	SEM	Raw	15min	30min	45min	SEM	Raw	5min	10min	15min	SEM
Crude protein (%)	28.10 ^b	28.30 ^b	28.47 ^{ab}	30.51 ^a	0.29	28.10 ^d	28.40 ^c	28.62 ^b	29.37 ^a	0.14	28.10 ^d	30.17 ^a	29.22 ^b	29.01 ^c	0.22
Ether extract (%)	2.10	2.14	2.15	2.21	0.02	2.10 ^b	2.12 ^b	2.11 ^b	2.20 ^a	0.01	2.10 ^b	2.21 ^a	2.13 ^{ab}	2.14 ^{ab}	0.01
Crude fibre (%)	7.49 ^d	7.61 ^c	7.84 ^b	10.11 ^a	0.32	7.49 ^d	7.52 ^c	7.69 ^b	9.88 ^a	0.30	7.49 ^d	10.00 ^a	8.01 ^c	8.97 ^b	0.29
Ash (%)	4.81 ^b	4.83 ^b	4.86 ^{ab}	5.23 ^a	0.05	4.81 ^b	5.00 ^a	5.14 ^a	5.17 ^a	0.24	4.81 ^b	5.54 ^{ab}	5.55 ^{ab}	5.61 ^a	0.10
Nitrogen Free extract (%)	50.11 ^a	49.12 ^b	48.80 ^c	44.42 ^d	0.66	50.11 ^a	49.07 ^b	48.54 ^c	45.60 ^d	0.50	50.11 ^a	44.95 ^d	47.99 ^b	47.23 ^c	0.56
Dry matter (%)	86.61 ^d	87.00 ^c	87.12 ^b	87.48 ^a	0.09	86.61 ^b	88.11 ^{ab}	88.10 ^{ab}	88.22 ^a	0.20	86.61 ^d	88.87 ^c	89.90 ^b	91.96 ^a	0.58
Phytochemicals															
Oxalate (mg/g)	2.43 ^a	1.71 ^b	1.54 ^c	1.20 ^d	0.14	2.43 ^a	2.07 ^b	1.53 ^c	0.90 ^d	0.17	2.43 ^a	1.08 ^{ab}	1.06 ^{ab}	0.81 ^b	0.19
Phytic acid (mg/g)	10.71 ^a	9.02 ^b	5.06 ^c	1.71 ^d	1.01	10.71 ^a	8.24 ^b	4.89 ^c	2.24 ^d	0.97	10.71 ^a	1.06 ^b	0.89 ^c	0.46 ^d	1.30
Saponin (mg/g)	24.72 ^a	2.97 ^b	2.40 ^c	1.63 ^d	2.92	24.72 ^a	2.55 ^b	2.09 ^c	0.91 ^d	2.99	24.72 ^a	1.63 ^b	1.32 ^c	0.85 ^d	3.06
Tannin (%)	4.17 ^a	0.45 ^b	0.39 ^c	0.21 ^d	0.49	4.17 ^a	1.03 ^b	0.98 ^c	0.92 ^d	0.42	4.17 ^a	1.17 ^d	1.20 ^c	1.35 ^b	0.38
Trypsin inhibitor (%)	29.40 ^a	11.16 ^b	5.09 ^c	2.70 ^d	2.97	29.40 ^a	13.11 ^b	5.71 ^c	2.01 ^d	2.90	29.40 ^a	1.61 ^b	1.41 ^c	1.01 ^d	0.01

Discussion

Pigeon pea seed meal (PPSM) has a high crude protein and ether extract concentration, according to

chemical analysis results. The range of protein values observed in this study (28.10–2.51%) was in agreement with the findings of Obioha (1992),

Amaefule and Obioha (2001), and Onu and Okongwu (2006), who reported a range of 17.90–30.00%. Akubor (2017) reported a value of crude protein to be 24.90% for toasted pigeon peas and 22.00% for boiled pigeon peas; the value in this study, however, was not consistent with those reported in the literature (Aduku, 1993; Olomu, 2011). It also confirms the potential of the meal as a rich protein feedstuff in animal feed. Variations may result from different agro climatic conditions and seed and cultivar storage techniques (Arora *et al.*, 1983).

Pigeon pea seed meal (PPSM) that had undergone various processing methods had low levels of trypsin, oxalate, phytate, saponin, and other inhibitors. This was consistent with the findings of Sgwane *et al.* (2008), who claimed that all members of the Leguminosae family still contain trace amounts of anti-nutrients. According to Al-Masri and Mardini (2013) anti-nutritional variables can have negative consequences and interfere with how well animals use their diet and produce. Before giving these drugs to the animals, they must be rendered inactive. In this study, the anti-nutritional factors in PPSM were reduced through processing. This finding was consistent with Akinmutimi's (2004) findings that anti-nutritional factors in legumes are typically reduced through soaking, sprouting, toasting, and cooking. When lentils were cooked, Wang *et al.* (2009) showed a similar outcome. Using dry heat to treat pigeon pea seeds resulted in a decrease in anti-nutritional factors, according to Egena *et al.*, (2007). Since anti-nutritional factors are known to influence monogastrics, this has a favorable impact. Animals' ability to absorb and use minerals has long been recognized to be inhibited by high levels of phytates and oxalates (Butler, 1989). Tannins lower the digestibility and palatability of protein, lowering its quality. When saponin concentrations are high, it damages cells by rupturing cell membranes, which stops cell proliferation (Mittal *et al.*, 2012). According to Farris and Singh (1990), trypsin inhibitors cause digestive losses by interfering with the activities of digestive enzymes. The test materials' concentrations of phytates, tannins, oxalates, saponins, and trypsin inhibitors were below the levels that would have a negative impact on their nutritional value or result in

any harmful effects linked to these anti-nutritional components. Additionally, the current findings are consistent with those made by Akinmutimi (2004), who discovered that while hazardous compounds were reduced after processing, it was not possible to completely eradicate all traces of anti-nutritional components from feedstuffs.

Conclusion

The proximate analysis of raw and processed pigeon pea seed meal (PPSM) showed that it had a high amount of crude protein (between 28.1 and 30.51%). Oxalate, phytate, saponin, tannin, and trypsin inhibitor levels in PPSM were lowered as a result of processing (soaking, boiling, and toasting).

Recommendation(S)

Due to its high crude protein content and excellent nutritional value, processed pigeon pea seed meal is advised for use as an ingredient in animal feed. To lessen the content of its anti-nutritional components, processing pigeon pea seeds by soaking, boiling, or toasting is advised.

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